

Educational Toolkit

reflect
connect
explore
share

for educators wishing to bring topics of diversity, equity, inclusion and belonging into their learning environments

Hello, Educators

Are you an educator looking for citizenship education-related content and teaching ideas on themes like diversity, migration, heritage, identity, belonging, and inclusion?

Are you passionate about giving those you teach space to explore themselves, others, and their place and roles in the world around them?

With the new citizenship education law in the Netherlands, school-based educators must now cover democracy, participation, and identity in our curricula. Some of us may have already been teaching about these topics for quite a while and are looking for fresh material. Others of us, meanwhile, may just be beginning to explore these topics, whether we really want to or not. Still, others of us may be informal educators and facilitators working with an array of civic organisations or perhaps supporting the inclusion of newcomers to the Netherlands. What do we need to know to support the development of those whose learning we facilitate as active, responsible 21st-century citizens?

It's not simply about covering new material. According to [SLO](#) (Landelijk Expertisecentrum Voor Het Curriculum), facilitating others' learning about citizenship also requires us, as formal/informal educators, to examine our own beliefs and behaviours when it comes to democracy, participation, and identity.

What kinds of citizens are we, and do we want to be? And what kinds of resources and guidance do we ourselves need to figure that out?

We're educators, not fortune-tellers. Yet, while we cannot know what complex political, economic, cultural and ecological futures lie ahead, we can help equip those within our care and ourselves to be able to navigate them. The Roots Guide Educational Toolkit is designed to help us gather and critically reflect on prior knowledge, to be curious about – and brave enough to explore – the situations we currently find ourselves in, and to imagine and prepare ourselves for futures that could emerge. This toolkit is intended to support both our personal growth as formal/informal educators and facilitators and the work we do with our diverse array of students and participants.

Content

Our Roots Guide approach	02
Take the first step yourself	03
About the toolkit methods	04
Your Roots Guide path	06
REFLECT	07
1: What do I want other people to really get about me?	09
2: What is my intersectional self?	11
3: How do I want to be seen in all my different facets?	13
STORY: Meet Abel	15
CONNECT	17
1: Map out the diversity	19
2: Share memories	20
3: Craft your story	21
4: Use empathetic listening	22
STORY: Meet Abdul	23
EXPLORE	26
1: What's the difference between past, history and heritage? And why does it matter?	28
2: What can we see if we look at the past through the lens of migration?	32
STORY: Meet Alina	37
SHARE	39
1: What I have gained	41
2: What we can give each other	42
STORY: Meet Carmen	43
The way forward	45
Acknowledgements	46

Our Roots Guide Approach

Both the Roots Guide guidebook and the Roots Guide Educational Toolkit's content and structure are informed by a global citizenship education (GCE) approach that combines cognitive, socio-emotional and behavioural learning in order to empower learners to assume active roles, both locally and globally, in building more peaceful, respectful, inclusive and secure societies.

- Cognitive learning equips learners to be informed and critically literate by acquiring and developing 'knowledge, understanding and critical thinking about global, regional, national and local issues and the interconnectedness and interdependence of different countries and populations' (UNESCO 2015: 15)
- Socio-emotional learning fosters learners' experience of 'a sense of belonging to a common humanity, sharing values and responsibilities, empathy, solidarity and respect for differences and diversity' (UNESCO 2015: 15)
- Behavioural learning focuses on enabling learners 'to act effectively and responsibly at local, national and global levels for a more peaceful and sustainable world' (UNESCO 2015: 15)

The Roots Guide Educational Toolkit focuses on the following GCE objectives:

- Distinguish between personal and collective identity and various social groups, appreciation and respect for difference and diversity
- Develop appreciation and respect for, as well as examine the benefits and challenges of, difference and diversity
- Cultivate empathy and solidarity towards other individuals and social groups
- Examine how individuals and groups have taken action on issues of local, national and global importance and get engaged in responses to local, national and global issues
- Analyse the challenges and dilemmas associated with social justice and ethical responsibility and consider the implications for individual and collective action.

Our toolkit is an educational companion to our Roots Guide guidebook, and both will forever be works-in-progress. Curriculum requirements, societies and global contexts change, and so do we. Therefore, resources and activities will be added and adapted over time.

Take the first step yourself

We encourage you, as an educator/facilitator, to do the REFLECT, CONNECT, EXPLORE and SHARE steps on your own - and, ideally, with your colleagues first. This gives you the opportunity to sensitise yourself to how your and others' intersectional experiences impact your and their learning processes and environments. It also enables you to more fully grasp what may be required - cognitively, emotionally and materially - to hold space for participants in ways appropriate to their interests, needs and resources so that they can bravely engage in exploration, forging empathetic connection and meaning-making.

The introspective and connective learning journey you and your participants are about to go on requires courage and vulnerability. Our invitations to you are the same as those we encourage you to extend to your participants:

- Put on your curiosity glasses
- Go as deep as feels comfortable to you at the moment
- Dare to ask questions
- Value progress over perfection

About the toolkit methods

Free writing

Free-writing is a stream-of-consciousness writing technique that allows us to quickly manifest and collect our thoughts and feelings in a non-linear way, without pressure to be accurate, structured or precise. It enables cognitive and emotional decompression and greater self-awareness. When doing it, we simply put our pens on the paper and write whatever comes in response to the prompt. No restrictions, no right or wrong, no overthinking - just let the mind wander and explore. Participants do not need to share their free-writing with anyone else - it is for themselves alone. However, it's good for them to keep in mind that they will be sharing some insights of their own choosing from their free-writing with others later.

Small-group sharing

Small-group sharing (or breakouts) provides participants with a more comfortable, intimate learning setting than when in plenary (or the whole group). In small groups, participants can feel freer to share their experiences in greater depth and at greater length, more actively engage in dialogue and more confidently brainstorm. Often working in pairs or trios, participants also develop more meaningful and lasting connections with one another as individuals. Generally, small-group sharing happens after initial content presentation and discussion in plenary and individual reflection moments, and then it's followed up with a plenary 'harvest' where small groups share their key learnings with the rest of the participants. This enables participants to 'digest' conceptual content by applying it to their own contexts and then to learn from and through each other's experiences.

About the toolkit methods

Creative methods

Creative methods (e.g., the creative, symbolic use of objects to prompt reflection, memory and dialogue; drawing, photography, visual storytelling and vlogging; creative writing; curating music playlists; collage; etc.) tap into abstract, embodied perception and experience in ways that assist participants to reflect on, describe, analyse and give meaning to their own experiences and perspectives. In addition to being engaging and fun techniques, they also stimulate imagination, awareness and appreciation of experiences and perspectives beyond their own.

Real Stories

Real people's stories enhance learning by providing relatable, tangible examples that humanise abstract concepts and inspire connection. Using stories not only makes learning more engaging and memorable, but it also enables appreciation of diverse perspectives, encourages critical thinking, and promotes more empathetic and inclusive learning environments.

Your Roots Guide path

01 Reflect

- 1: What do I want other people to really get about me?
- 2: What is my intersectional self?
- 3: How do I want to be seen in all my different facets?

02 Connect

- 1: Map out the diversity
- 2: Share memories
- 3: Craft your story
- 4: Use empathetic listening

03 Explore

- 1: What's the difference between past, history and heritage? And why does it matter?
- 2: What can we see if we look at the past through a lens of migration?

04 Share

- 1: What I have gained?
- 2: What we can give each other?

01

REFLECT

Let's start to REFLECT on your intersectional identity and how you wish to be seen by others. The REFLECT process consists of a set of 3 activities (2.7-3.5 hours in total):

Activities

Learning Objectives

1: What do I want other people to really get about me?

Fosters personal connection with your own and others' current and previous experiences and feelings relative to identity, difference and stereotyping

2: What is my intersectional self?

Helps you see yourself and others through an intersectional lens - i.e., how society shapes what each of us can be/do as a result of the intersection of different facets of our identities

3: How do I want to be seen in all my different facets?

Enables you to reflect on how you want to represent yourself and articulate this to someone else, and recognise how you represent others

99

“My mom told me to be careful when I went out. I noticed that people crossed the street when they saw me, only to cross back again after I had passed. I guess their parents must have given them the same advice, but apparently I’m the one they have to be careful of.

Some people tried to ‘reassure’ me: “You’re not that black.” “Ok, your nose and your hair are a little bit...” “Yeah, but you got freckles.” Sure, please tell me more about who I am. All of these experiences made me think about my identity. I had never given skin colour much thought before. Now all of a sudden, I was too white for the blacks and too black for the whites.”

– Abel

1: What do I want other people to get about *me*?

PART 1

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Purpose

To foster personal connection with your own and others' current and previous experiences and feelings relative to identity, difference and stereotyping

Outcome

Engage in individual written reflection and collective oral reflection Identify similarities and differences between your own and others' experiences

Time

26-30 minutes in total

- Part 1: 10 minutes for the introduction to free-writing and response to 4 free-writing prompts
- Part 2: 16-20 minutes for small-group sharing and dialogue

Material

- Blank sheets of paper or personal notebooks and something to write with for each participant
- Quiet space to reflect individually and later to share in pairs/trios
- Something to keep time (watch or smartphone)

Preparation

- Put prompt questions on a slide/whiteboard/flipchart in such a way that you reveal them question by question
- Ensure sufficient paper and writing supplies are at hand for all participants

Group Size

- 2+ people

Start with a free-writing exercise. Explain what free-writing is and what it enables before starting. Remind participants that they do not need to share the free-writing with anyone else - it is for themselves alone. However, it's good for them to keep in mind that they will be sharing some insights from their free-writing with others in small groups later.

Then, provide a few sheets of blank paper or ask participants to use their notebooks in order to do some free-writing on each of the following questions (put them on a slide and reveal only one question at a time to ensure focus on the specific question at hand):

- When you meet new people, what do you really want them to understand about you? And how do you react when someone is only interested in where you come from? (2 minutes)
- In what places and when do you feel you can really be yourself? (2 minutes)
- Think about one of the first times that you felt different from others. What caused it? (2 minutes)
- What stereotypes have you personally experienced? What feelings ran through you? (2 minutes)

PART 2

Divide the group into pairs or trios. Then follow the steps below for this small-group sharing exercise:

- In these small groups, each participant will take turns speaking, uninterrupted, for 3 minutes to allow for free flow of thoughts and ideas to emerge based on the social identity wheel questions they reflected on. Others in the group actively listen in service of the one who is speaking. Have one person act as a timekeeper with their watch or smartphone timer to ensure that each person has equal time to speak.
- After a person has spoken, the listeners reflect back (1 minute per listener) on the speakers what they have seen, sensed and heard the speaker convey; the listeners refrain from giving suggestions, ideas, or relating to their own experiences.
- The speaker then reflects on what they have heard from the listeners (1 minute in total).
- This cycle is repeated until each person has been in a speaker role.
- Following this, everyone in the small group does some individual free-writing or drawing (2 minutes) to reflect on what they've taken from the sharing experience.
- To wrap up, participants in the small group share briefly (5-10 minutes in total for the group) about what stays with them and what they'd like to explore further. Potential prompts to support this include:
 - What are the commonalities and differences you notice?
 - What did the others' reflections allow you to see that you didn't see before?
 - What do you realise about your identities, feelings of difference and experience with stereotypes?

2: What is my intersectional self?

Purpose

To see yourself and others through an intersectional lens - i.e., how society shapes what each of us can be/do as a result of the intersection of different facets of our identities

Outcome

- Consider the ways in which different facets of your identities are more or less keenly felt in different social contexts
- Pay attention to the range of identities that you acquire and identities that you claim/cultivate
- Examine how privilege operates to normalise some of your identities over others

Time

50-65 minutes in total

- Part 1: 15 minutes for the free-writing, depending on the need to respond to clarifying questions about terminology
- Part 2: Brief 3-minute introduction, then small-group sharing (20 minutes/pair or 30 minutes/trio)
- Part 3: Harvesting small-group learnings and reflecting on definitions in plenary (15-20 minutes)

Material

- Printed-out A4 copy of the [social identity wheel](#) (See [LSA University of Michigan Inclusive Learning for complete instructions](#) - 'Option B')
- Blank paper and something to write with
- Quiet space to reflect individually and later to share in pairs/trios
- A watch or smartphone to keep timeTape to hang definitions on the wall

Preparation

Print out 1 copy of the social identity wheel per person

Group Size

- 2+ people

Have participants familiarise themselves with the social identity wheel handout (7 minutes). Ask if anyone has questions about the terminology before moving on and, as a group, try to give examples to illustrate a term without necessarily trying to define it.

Then, provide a few sheets of blank paper for them to do some free-writing on each of the following questions (put them on a slide and reveal only one question at a time to ensure focus on the specific question at hand):

- What identities do you think about most often? (2 minutes)
- What identities do you think about least often? (2 minutes)
- What identities would you like to learn more about? (2 minutes)
- What identities have the strongest effect on how you perceive yourself? (2 minutes)
- What identities have the greatest effect on how others perceive you? (2 min.)

PART 2

Have participants partner up in pairs or trios to share with each other. Then, follow the steps below for this small-group sharing exercise:

- In these small groups, each participant will take turns speaking, uninterrupted, for 3 minutes to allow for free flow of thoughts and ideas to emerge based on the social identity wheel questions they reflected on. Others in the group actively listen in service of the one who is speaking.
- After a person has spoken, the listeners reflect back (1 minute per listener) on the speakers what they have seen, sensed and heard the speaker convey; the listeners refrain from giving suggestions, ideas, or relating to their own experiences.
- The speaker then reflects on what they have heard from the listeners (1 minute in total).
- This cycle is repeated until each person has been in a speaker role.
- Following this, everyone in the small group does some individual free-writing or drawing (2 minutes) to reflect on what they've taken from the sharing experience.
- To wrap up, participants in the small group share briefly (5 minutes in total for the group) about what stays with them and what they'd like to explore further. Potential prompts to support this include:
 - What are the commonalities and differences you notice?
 - What did the others' reflections allow you to see that you didn't see before?
 - What do you realise about the intersections of your different identities?
- The small group then develops very rough definitions for the following terms: 'identity', 'privilege', and 'representation' (5 minutes in total). These are written down on A4 sheets of paper in a way that they can be easily read.

PART 3

In plenary, each group posts their definitions on the wall – definitions of the same term are grouped together. All participants take a few minutes to silently read the definitions. They, again silently, can add to the posted definitions with post-it notes if they feel something may be missing. Depending on the time available, you may wish to facilitate a group discussion about the definitions that emerged. (15-20 minutes)

3: How do I want to be seen in all my different facets?

Purpose

To be able to reflect on how you want to represent yourself and articulate this to someone else, and to recognise how you represent others

Outcome

- Be able to articulate to someone else how you want to represent yourself, in consideration of the different facets you wish to have recognised
- Take a portrait of a person that reflects how they really wish to be seen
- Have a portrait taken of you that reflects how you really wish to be seen

Time

85-110 minutes total, depending on group size

- Part 1: 10 minutes to watch brief video and collectively discuss, then 10 to reflect on earlier writing and briefly sharing in plenary
- Part 2: 45-60 minutes to take portraits of one another
- Part 3: 20-30 minutes to share and reflect on the portraits in plenary

Material

- Participants' free-writing responses to earlier prompts
- Filled-out social identity wheel by each participant
- Personal objects/photos for each participant
- Smartphone or digital camera for each participant
- Beamer, blank wall and computer with internet connection

Preparation

- Participants are invited to use what they wrote earlier in the session about how they wish to be seen (Activity 1) and their social identity wheel (Activity 2)
- Participants may wish to bring with them personal objects/photos relevant to Activity 3
- Have the short video 'Starting spark: Nikon Photo Stereotypes' available at [Print out 1 copy of the social identity wheel per person](#) ready to screen
- Set up an online folder with Google Drive or similar to which participants can upload the portraits they've selected to represent themselves

Group Size

- 2+ people

PART 1

Start by having the group watch this [3-minute video called 'Starting spark: Nikon Photo Stereotypes'](#). Dedicate 5 minutes to discussing what the group sees, senses and feels about it.

Next, invite participants to silently revisit what they wrote earlier in the session about their social identities and how they wish to be seen (5 minutes). Then encourage a few participants to share about how others perceive/'frame' them and to what extent those perceptions are similar to or different from how they actually wish to be seen (5 minutes).

PART 2

Organise participants into small groups (pairs or trios). Their objective: take a portrait of the other person that reflects how that person really wishes to be seen, and have a portrait taken of you that reflects how you really wish to be seen (45-60 minutes). Each participant tries to communicate what about themselves they want to be captured in a photo and the others try to do that. Consider angle, lighting, setting, props, facial expressions and gestures, etc. The person being photographed decides which photo is the best at capturing who they are.

PART 3

Invite everyone back and have them share with the group the portrait that most closely represents them as they wish to be represented (20-30 minutes). They may wish to upload the portrait to an online folder so that the photos can be easily accessed and screened during the session. Discuss the processes they went through in order to take a portrait that most closely represented someone else.

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Meet **Abel**

All I remember were the police cars around me, and the faint cries of my mom in the background.

My mom was born in Noordwijk in the Netherlands. Expectations were set high, but she never truly lived up to those. Her sister went to university, while she went to community college. Her sister studied law, while she studied to become a nurse. Her sister chose a rich white man, while she chose a black man. My mom and dad met at the hospital where he went to get his heart checked. He was born in Curaçao and moved to the Netherlands at the age of 19. That's all I know of my father's early life. My parents moved to Haarlem, which I saw for the first time in 1992. As a kid I loved playing make belief games and draw with colourful crayons in the street. I went to school on the back of my mum's bike, and I 'married' my teacher in kindergarten. At home, I played with my Super Nintendo Entertainment System or my Gameboy. But I preferred to be outdoors or go

to my friends' house. "Home, sweet home" didn't apply to me, since home was far from a safe space. My father was not a good man. And -- I was bullied at school. I never felt relaxed.

One day, like any other, we suddenly heard someone yelling outside. My sister and I were watching TV, while my mom was cooking and my father sat in his chair. "You fucking niggers come outside, I'll gut you!" The whole room tensed up. "I'll kill your son and make you watch me rape your wife and daughter." At this point my mom was ringing the police, while my father made a beeline for the drawer and grabbed a knife. I sat in shock on the couch. I didn't know what to do. Then I saw my neighbour and his son through the kitchen window. They were yelling more profanities and both were wielding knives.

All I remember were the police cars around me, and the faint cries of my mom in the background.

Over the following years situations like these became a regular part of my life. My mom told me to be careful when I went out. I noticed that people crossed the street when they saw me, only to cross back again after I had passed. I guess their parents must have given them the same advice, but apparently I'm the one they have to be careful of. Some people tried to 'reassure' me: "You're not that black." "Ok, your nose and your hair are a little bit..." "Yeah, but you got freckles." Sure, please tell me more about who I am. All of these experiences made me think about my identity. I had never given skin color much thought before. Now all of a sudden, I was too white for the blacks and too black for the whites.

When I was in highschool, one of the rituals I had with my mom was to go to the Cronjé shopping street every Saturday. We'd go to Kruidvat to get my shampoo, get a milkshake, and if I put on my puppy eyes, maybe my mom would get me a video game. But this particular Saturday was different. Game Mania had just opened its first video game store in the Netherlands, here in my neighborhood. My eyes widened. "Maybe you'll work here some day, sweetie," my mom said. I distinctly remember telling her:

"No, this is for the cool kids." High school wasn't very challenging, so my motivation was low. I did make a couple of tight friends, but when I dropped out of school, my friends dropped me as well. After all these years trying to figure out where I belonged, I thought I had found my place. I hadn't.

About a year later, I walked into Game Mania. I grabbed a copy of Street Fighter and walked up to the checkout. As I handed it over to the guy behind the counter, his eyes widened. "No way man," he said, "have you played this before?"

"No," I replied, "I've played older versions, but not this one." I noticed a couple of heads started turning around behind the counter, revealing a TV they were playing that exact game on. "Dude! Go home and practice for a little bit and come by next Thursday, that's when we all get together and play!" he said as he extended his hand. "My name's Tom by the way." That Thursday when I came back to the store, I was greeted by Tom and five other guys of all ages, races and religions. They were excited to see me and wanted to play me to see how good I'd gotten in a week. I immediately felt at ease with the excitement the others showed by shouting things like "Oh, that was close!" and "Good job man!" It made me feel like I belonged. "We still have that open position by the way" one of the employees said. "Are you looking for people to work here?" I blurted out. "If you beat me I'll consider it," Tom said. I played my ass off, but in the end I lost. Tom still asked me for my resume. A week later I started my job at the place for the cool kids.

The Street Fighter logo is now tattooed on my shoulder. That job at Game Mania changed my life forever. I've met so many wonderful people through that store over the years. People from different backgrounds who make me feel that I belong, because we share a common interest. People that are my family today. It's the reason I consider Haarlem MY home and MY city now. Home, to me, is a place or a person that makes you feel safe to be yourself.

02 CONNECT

You've taken time to REFLECT on your social identity. Now, let's dig deeper. The purpose of CONNECT is to facilitate (re)connection with your own life stories. The CONNECT process consists of a set of 4 activities (2.5-3 hours in total) to help everyone to dig deeper into their personal experience:

Activities

Learning Objectives

1: Map out the diversity

Recognise the range of identities and lived experiences in your group.

2: Share memories

Spark stories of your personal connections to migration.

3: Craft your story

(Re)connect with the wealth of your own lived experiences.

4: Use empathetic listening

Understand and connect with others more deeply.

“In the beginning it was challenging, I was not comfortable talking about emotional stuff. Now I am happy I was part of sharing my story, because you think you know everything about yourself, but then you discover something new.”

– *Abdul*

1: Map out the diversity.

Purpose

To recognise the range of identities and lived experiences in your group

Outcome

- Get to know each other on a personal level
- Recognise diversity that's not visible to the eye

Time

20-30 minutes

Material

Open space to be able to stand in a circle

Preparation

Make a list of ten questions (or use those we suggest below), and then invite participants to ask questions they would like to know more about their peers

Group Size

- 6-100 people

Kick off your storytelling process with an ice breaker that gently brings about little insights and 'aha' moments - individually and collectively.

Invite everyone to stand in a circle. Read out a few statements inviting participants who recognise themselves with the statement to step into the circle. After each statement, take a moment to see who stepped into the circle, and who did not. Then after a few statements, open it up for anyone to suggest a statement. It is a great way to get to know each other and brings awareness of diversity in the group and encourages inclusion by showing our invisible experiences and identities.

Suggested statements

- Speaks more than two languages
- Is more introverted than extroverted
- Has a (grand)parent born outside the Netherlands
- Has lived part of their lives outside the Netherlands
- Belongs to communities of faith
- Belongs to sport communities
- Is an only child
- Has experienced exclusion
- Grew up in the countryside
- Invite participants to suggest other questions.

Inclusivity tip: This activity can be done in different ways. If physical mobility is not possible by all participants, you can ask people to raise their hands instead.

Tip: You can transform this into a storytelling event. And invite people to share little stories for each sentence.

2: Share *memories.*

Purpose

To bring up memories that spark stories of personal connection to migration

Outcome

- Get to know each other on a deeper personal level
- Recognise diversity that's not visible to the eye
- Share three personal anecdotes connected to your personal experiences with migration

Time

45 minutes

Material

3 photos

Preparation

Prior to the session, invite participants to bring three photos from their own lives to the session related to:

- Your (grand)parents and ancestors
- A childhood memory about something that has shaped who you are today
- What you want people to really get about you

Group Size

- 2+

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Now that the ice has been broken, let's dig a little deeper into the insights and 'aha!' moments and how they are connected to our personal connections to migration.

Divide everyone into pairs or small groups. Invite them to share their three photos with each other, why they chose those photos, and the stories behind them. After each person has shared, they are free to ask questions to get to know the storyteller in more depth. This is a beautiful way to let everyone start (re-)connecting with their own stories and how they are shaped by them as well as starting to connect with each other.

Once everyone has finished their group sharing, harvest insights and experiences in the bigger group.

3: Craft your story.

Purpose

To (re-)connect with the wealth of your lived experiences

Outcome

Visualise your life story and identify key transition moments in your life

Time

20-40 minutes, depending on session length

Material

- Blank paper (A3 or A2 in size)
- Colourful markers

Preparation

- Blank paper (A3 or A2 in size)
- Colourful markers

Group Size

- 2+

Time for story discovery and drafting!

Gather everyone into a circle and explain that they will now go into an interactive activity to discover and draft their own stories. Invite everyone to take a big piece of paper and a few markers, then give them 20-40 minutes to draw their own journey. This means having them identify the key events, milestones, people, communities, etc., that have brought them to become the individuals they are today. Participants can be as creative as they wish, but invite them to minimise the use of words and give priority to images.

Remind participants when there are 5 minutes left. Then, when the time is up, gather them back in a circle and explain the next part of the activity.

4: Use empathetic listening.

Purpose

To practise empathetic listening skills to understand others more deeply

Outcome

- Learn how to express yourself freely
- Gain a better understanding of yourself and your own experiences
- Find common ground between yourself and the storyteller

Time

60 minutes

Material

- Blank paper
- Colourful markers

Preparation

Print-outs, slides or flipchart/whiteboard with the empathetic guidelines as a reference

Group Size

- 2+

Time for story discovery!

Gather back in the circle. Go through the Empathetic Listening Guidelines (see below). Then, divide people into pairs or trios. These groups will be together for the next 60 minutes to share their personal journeys. They take turns being storytellers, empathetic listeners and timekeepers. Each storyteller gets 10 minutes to present and another 10 minutes to receive and respond to questions from those listening. In any remaining time, the small groups can dig further into each other's stories.

Empathetic listening guidelines

- Start with: 'Tell me about you - what do you want others to really "get" about you?'
- Ask open-ended questions to dig deeper into their experiences.
- Ask about feelings.
- Use 'Tell me more', rather than 'Why'.
- Avoid 'usually' and 'normally'.
- Don't give advice or try to solve problems.
- Don't be afraid of silence.
- Be present, listening with body and mind.
- Words spoken by the storyteller: 95%, by the listener: 5%.
- Help the storyteller feel more heard than ever before.

Meet

Abdul

At 7:00 in the morning Abdul takes a quick shower before he eats his breakfast together with his mother. She leaves at 7:30 am for work, while Abdul spends the remaining 28 minutes playing computer games. At 7:58 am he grabs his backpack and runs the mere ten meters to his school. This morning routine lasted until he turned 17 and had to leave home for good. Today, Abdul sits in the Netherlands and has spent hours walking in Utrecht processing what he left behind.

Abdul Malek Altawekij was born in 1997 in Hama, the fourth biggest city in Syria known for its ancient wooden water mills that used to irrigate the ancient city gardens. Abdul had a carefree childhood as he grew up in a peaceful time, which he mostly spent with his family, friends or at school. "Nearly all my friends went to the same school, so we almost had too much fun." Abdul was very fond of computer science as it felt a bit like magic, but he was a bit disappointed about the outdated books the school provided. In combination with a teacher who could barely turn the computer on and off, Abdul and his friends decided to take it upon themselves to expand their IT knowledge through the magic that is the internet. Not long after they were setting up LANs and designing their own computer games. Whenever the teacher asked what they were doing, they quickly switched tabs and pretended to do their homework. Life was good, fueled by a steady supply of aromatic arabic coffee Abdul and his friends would play games, study and have fun.

Despite the wars raging in the neighbouring countries, life in Syria was peaceful. Young Abdul knew very little about the Palestinian and Iraqi refugees that were seeking safety in Syria en masse. Like almost everyone else, he was unaware that Syria was about to take a similar path as its neighbours. In 2011, when Abdul was 13 years old the war broke out. "I was too young to fully understand what was going on. The first couple of years most people did not leave Syria, and we tried to live as normal lives as possible in the hope for a peaceful solution." As the war escalated, however, Abdul and his family went from barely noticing people leaving Syria to spending the whole day talking about where everyone had gone.

Life in Hama started to change drastically as the radical religious groups that were forming

in different parts of Syria started to frequent the city outskirts. When Abdul graduated high school during all the turmoil, he was listed the 9th best high school student in Syria. The initial excitement was quickly replaced with disappointment and fear, when he realised that he had to commute through the many checkpoints with his Sunni identity cards in the Shia dominated areas to his university. The thought of days of interrogation and kidnapping terrified the Altawekij family. And even if he would make it safely through the checkpoints, there was always the risk of being bombed, just as the friend of Abdul's brother's school bus was. On top of it, by rule of the Syrian government, outstanding graduates were obliged to enrol in specific studies at university, which made Abdul's situation seem even more hopeless.

If he wanted to both secure his future and stay safe, Abdul needed to leave. He first considered neighbouring countries like Iraq, Jordan or Turkey, but they were either in crisis themselves or had stopped accepting Syrians altogether by then. "I honestly wanted to stay in Syria, but education was extremely important for me so I kept looking for an alternative." While searching online for education opportunities, he noticed there were few complaints about the Netherlands in comparison to other countries such as Germany, Sweden, etc. "It wouldn't be too bad living in the country of the runner-up of the 2010 World Cup," Abdul thought to himself.

With a heavy heart, 17 year-old Abdul left his family and friends as he embarked upon his quest for freedom. For 13 days he travelled by car, train, taxi and foot to complete the 4010 km journey from Hama to Amsterdam. At the end of the trip, Abdul found himself standing at Amsterdam Central station feeling lost and alone.

Everything felt strange and unknown, until a familiar green and white logo suspended over platform one grabbed his attention. “We don’t have Starbucks in Syria, but I have seen it in the movies many times.” The familiarity gave Abdul a feeling of safety, and he thought to himself: “I think I’ve deserved a caffeinated treat after my trip.” Going without coffee for almost two weeks was a personal record for Abdul, but it was not quite long enough to enjoy uninspired coffee. After he threw away his unfinished coffee he noticed another logo that said “Police.”

While Abdul awaited the outcome of his refugee application, he furiously tried to master the pronunciation of ‘vreemdelingen identiteitsbewijs’ and other relevant Dutch vocabulary and grammar. Additionally, he researched which universities provided interesting studies. When he discovered that the Technische Universiteit van Eindhoven was one of the world’s best universities for computer science, Abdul excitedly contacted the Stichting voor Vluchtelingen-Studenten (UAF) for advice. To his great despair, he was told it would be very difficult to get enrolled in university and that he should consider completing an MBO and finding a job instead. While Abdul understood UAF’s concerns, he hadn’t come this far to give up on his dream. At the Open Day at the TU Eindhoven, he introduced himself to a nice lady and told her about his aspirations. “We already have a few Syrian students here,” she told him, “You just have to do some math courses and English exams.” “I passed them and got accepted!” Abdul proclaims delightedly.

The Netherlands opened many new doors for Abdul, but without his will to push himself into the unknown he would not be where he is today. Abdul’s journey has shaped him in ways he couldn’t have imagined a few years back. “I have become a lot more responsible than I was in Syria, particularly considering my age.” When asked where he found the courage to share his story, he answers: “In the beginning it was challenging, I was not comfortable talking about emotional stuff. Now I am happy I was part of sharing my story, because you think you know everything about yourself, but then you discover something new.”

His courageous steps to discover the world outside home, as well as the world within himself has taught Abdul that sometimes walking 10 metres is not enough to grow, you need to go out into the unknown and fight for what you need. As Abdul himself says, “Why not? What do you have to lose?”

03

EXPLORE

You've taken time to CONNECT with your personal stories. Beautiful! Now, let's explore how they're connected to our past, history and heritage. The purpose of EXPLORE is to facilitate the exploration of the past through the lens of our personal migration stories. The EXPLORE process consists of two activities (2-2.5 hours in total):

Activities

1: What's the difference between past, history and heritage? And why does it matter?

2: What can we see if we look at the past through the lens of migration?

Learning Objectives

Understand how the narratives we tell ourselves about who we are are never neutral.

Situate personal, family/ancestral and community experiences within a broader social, economic and political historical context

99

The Soviet Union had just fallen and the borders were opening up. Suddenly many people were moving to Germany and Israel. 'Everyone' seemed to know someone who had moved abroad. One day my mum picked me up from primary school. She told me that we too were getting out of here. My reaction was 'yeah sure'! But one month later I moved from present-day Lithuania to an industrial town called Nizhny Tagil in Russia, 1800km from Moscow. I would stay there with grandma. My mom is going to the Netherlands to build a future for us.

- Alina

1: What's the difference between past, history and heritage? *And why does it matter?*

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Start out with making reference to the [slide](#) or [print-out](#) of this quote and ask participants to discuss what it means to them (5 min.):

“

‘History is composed of facts the way that a cathedral is composed of bricks, let's say. But the bricks are not the cathedral. The cathedral is something about the way the bricks are put together. So history, in that sense, is a narrative, is a story, and I am undertaking to tell that story. And it's not the only way to tell it, but it's maybe one way’.

– Tamim Ansary,
author of [The Invention of Yesterday](#)

Purpose

To understand how the narratives we tell ourselves about who we are are never neutral

Outcome

Understand the differences between past, history and heritage
Increase awareness of migration history and heritages over time in relation to the Netherlands

Time

Understand the differences between past, history and heritage
Increase awareness of migration history and heritages over time in relation to the Netherlands

Material

- Beamer and computer
- Something to write with for each participant
- [Slides for Part 1](#)

Preparation

- Set up beamer
- Download and use the slide deck above

Group Size

- 2+

PART 1

Make reference to the [slide](#) or [print-out](#) with the following text (5 min.):

Here's the basic distinction between past, history and heritage:

- **Past:** Everything that happened before now.
- **History:** The study of what happened in the past – used to develop a narrative of how a particular thing came into being, how it evolved over time, and what made it what it is today.
- **Heritage:** Something (e.g., object, monument, custom, song, story, etc.) that has survived from the past – a group or society inherits it from previous generations and it contributes to the group's identity.

Provide participants with blank paper and something to write or draw with. Invite participants to take 5 minutes to come up with a good example or two from their own lives, that of their family/ancestors or communities with which they identify to distinguish between these three different concepts. Have them write about or draw it.

Then, divide participants into pairs and have them take 6-10 minutes to share their examples with one other person in the group. Designate a timekeeper within each group to ensure that each trio member has equal time (3-5 minutes per person) to share.

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Next, make reference to the [slide](#) or [print-out](#) with the following text and discuss it with the group (5 min.):

Why does differentiating between past, history and heritage matter?

The stories we tell about ourselves and others are never neutral. They shape how we perceive, and act in relation to, the past, present and future as well as the people and places in them.

Here are two key concepts that help us understand what is at stake and for whom:

- **Authorised heritage discourse:** Those with power (e.g., people, institutions, governments, industries, media, etc.) construct and spread interpretations of the past that serve their current agendas.
- **Dissonant heritage:** When different groups have differing interpretations/stories about something (e.g., object, monument, custom, tradition, etc.) and there is little space for multiple interpretations, tensions develop over whose interpretation is more accurate.

Provide participants with blank paper and something to write or draw with. Invite participants to spend 5 minutes doing some individual free-writing or drawing about everything they personally know about migration in and out of the Netherlands over time.

PART 2

Then, make reference to the [slide](#) with the following prompts to have them do some more free-writing or drawing:

- How are people and places portrayed? Whose perspectives are privileged, and whose are marginalised or absent? (Authorised heritage discourse) (2 minutes)
- From what sources have I learned about migration? What might be their stakes and objectives in telling stories about migration in the way they have? (Authorised heritage discourse) (2 minutes)
- Do I notice any differences between what I've been told by others about migration and what I've experienced in my own life or seen in the lives of my family members/ancestors and communities with which I identify? (Dissonant heritage) (2 minutes)

Next, divide the group into trios. Dedicate 15-20 minutes for trio members to take a critical look at what they've written or drawn and have them reflect on their responses to the prompts above. Designate a timekeeper within each group to ensure that each trio member has equal time (3-5 minutes per person) to share. Any remaining time can be used in the trios for dialogue.

Source: Rehab Eldalil

2: What can we see if we look at the past through the lens of migration?

Purpose

To situate personal, family/ancestral and community experiences within a broader social, economic and political historical context

Outcome

Develop a collective timeline of meaningful experiences/events in your personal, family/ancestral and communities' lives over time Identify the similarities and diversity among types and perspectives relative to participants' personal, family/ancestral and communities' meaningful experiences/events

Time

65-80 minutes (not including approx. 60+ minutes prior to the session to read the key text for the session)

Material

- Printer and blank printer paper
- Beamer and computer
- Something to write with for each participant
- Long roll of blank paper for the timeline
- Tape or glue to affix stories to the timeline
- Print-outs of the key text for the session
- Print-outs of story templates
- Slides for the session

Preparation

- Share the print-ready document of the key text for the session with participants prior to the session so that they have read it before coming
- Download and print out the short key migration periods texts (i.e., Periods 1-6) from the document above, cut them apart, and organise them on a long piece of paper to make a timeline before the session begins
- Download and print out at least 2 story templates of each kind of story (personal, family/ancestral, community) per participant for them to be able to fill in during the session
- Download the slides for the session and set up the beamer

Group Size

- 2+

PART 1

Discuss the the following text (see [print-ready document](#)) (5 min.):

More than 25% of the population living in the Netherlands today has a first- or second-generation migration background, meaning that many of us or our parents were born outside of the Netherlands. However, up until very recently, little attention has been given in schools and in public life about the role that migration has played in shaping the Netherlands' history and heritages.

This means that many of us don't get to see the diversity of our origins and our ancestors' lived experiences represented in the classroom, the media, etc. What makes this lack of attention to migration even stranger is that migration is not something that's recently been introduced to the Netherlands.

In fact, the people and places in the territory that the Netherlands occupies today have been shaped for millennia by migration in its various forms and motivations: trade, conquest, conversion, conflict, colonisation, slavery, learning, love, solidarity, etc.

Invite participants to do some free-writing or drawing (5 minutes) about how these migration forms and motivations may have shaped their lives as well as those of their family, ancestors and the communities with which they identify. Encourage them to consider, for example, the language(s) you speak; how they dress; what you eat; the customs, values and rules of law you follow; the music you listen to; etc.

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Then invite participant to engage with the following text (see [print-ready document](#)) - see full step-by-step instructions below this text:

What does the Netherlands look like through a lens of migration? Many educators use the [Canon van Nederland](#)'s material to teach about the Netherlands' history and heritages to students from Group 5 (ages 8-9) onwards. Yet, before its recent revision, the Canon van Nederland barely mentioned migration in its varied forms. Rather, it framed migration mainly as something that, starting with the guest workers (gastarbeiders) in the mid-20th century, brought 'colour' to the country. However, as [Vijf Eeuwen Migratie](#) points out, more than 98% of people living in the Netherlands have ancestors that migrated – meaning that 'traces of migration can be found everywhere'.

We present a very [brief overview](#) of what we, informed by Vijf Eeuwen Migratie and other scholarly work (see [References](#)), understand as key periods of migration that shape the past, present and future of people living in the Netherlands today. We then provide a table that helps you draw links between these periods, the Canon van Nederland and Roots Guide 'Connect' stories that can help you really bring history to life for yourself and others whose learning you're facilitating.

Table 1. Key periods and moments in migration history and heritage linked to the Netherlands

Key periods and moments of migration relative to the Netherlands	Associated Canon van Nederland 'windows' ('vensters')	Associated Roots Guide 'Connect' stories
1. Dutch colonisation in Asia (1602-1949), followed by Indonesian independence (1949)	VOC en WIC (1602-1799) Slavernij (1637-1863) Max Havelaar (1860)	In the book: Antis, Jootje, Wendy
2. Dutch colonisation in the Americas (1637-Present), followed by Suriname's independence (1975) and the continued presence of the Netherlands in the Caribbean today	VOC en WIC (1602-1799) Slavernij (1637-1863) Anton de Kom Het Caribisch gebied (sinds 1945)	In the book: Jennifer, Jill, Noukhey, Lay, Henk In the toolkit: Abel
3. Intra-European religious, ethnic and political persecution during the Reformation and Inquisition (1500-1700), the First World War (1914-18) and the Second World War (1939-45)	De Eerste Wereldoorlog (1914-1918) De Tweede Wereldoorlog (1940-1945) Anne Frank (1929-1945)	In the book: Luise
5. Humanitarian crises, asylum migration and adoption (1980s-Present)	Srebrenica (1995)	In the book: Claudius, Hans, Marina, Marrit, Masood, Razan, Sami, Sarah In the toolkit: Abdul
4. Economic emigration and immigration in the aftermath of the Second World War (1945-1973), followed by family reunification (1970s)	De Gastarbeiders (vanaf 1960)	In the book: Nebi, Barbara, Jan, Laura, Funda In the toolkit: Alina
6. Mobility within the European Union (2000s-Present)	Europa (since 1945)	In the book: Mart, Niels, Mila, Roderik, Rita, Wolter, Nga

Have everyone individually read the short texts with the 6 key periods and moments in migration history and heritage linked to the Netherlands (see above) prior to the session. Supplement the reading with content from [Canon van Nederland](#) and [Roots Guide](#) 'CONNECT' stories.

Before your participants come together, print out the short key migration periods texts (i.e., Periods 1-6), cut them apart, and organise them on a long piece of paper to make a timeline.

When the participants are together during the session, have everyone collectively identify a list of what they perceive as significant international social, economic and political events/periods and approximately when they occurred in the past. They can be more recent and go very far back into the past. (Have the group generate a list of the 15-20 most important events/periods to not make the timeline too complicated collectively.) Then, have them add these by hand to the top of the timeline. (10-15 minutes)

Dedicate 20-30 minutes for participants to write down and add to the timeline some key personal, family/ancestral and community stories. Use the [story templates](#) for the different kinds of stories generated, if you like. To support participants' reflection process, you may wish to use this set of prompts (see the slide):

- **Conquest:** Can you recognise the influences of conquest, trade, exchange and migration in your native language(s), cuisine and customs?
- **Colonisation and independence:** What have you, your communities and families experienced relative to colonisation and independence from colonial rule?
- **Religious/political exile and asylum:** Have you, or did anyone from your communities and families experience religious or political exile or asylum?
- **Armed conflict:** Have you, or did anyone from your communities and families experience armed conflict? **Economic migration:** Did you or anyone from your communities and families migrate somewhere else for economic reasons? How were you/they treated?
- **Regional integration:** What has being in the European Union meant for you? What challenges and what privileges?

Affix the participants' resulting anecdotes/stories approximately when they happened along the timeline. Then, give time for the group to read the stories on the timeline silently. (15 minutes)

Hold space for small and then large group reflective dialogue on what they notice, sense and feel. Identify what sparks each of the participants to want to learn more about regarding the relationship between their (and others') stories and the broader social, economic and political contexts in which they occurred. (20 minutes)

At the end of the session, encourage participants to dig deeper now and explore those sparks by reading further; connecting with experts and people with lived experience; and visiting sites, museums and archives, etc. Then, go to SHARE for ideas for how participants can digest and communicate their learning in diverse formats of expression to be able to share it with others (peers, family, community) in meaningful, accessible ways.

Adding personal, family/ancestral, and community stories to a collective narrative timeline. (Source: Meghann Ormond, 2022, for Migrantour Utrecht)

Story

Meet

Alina

The Soviet Union had just fallen and the borders were opening up. Suddenly many people were moving to Germany and Israel. 'Everyone' seemed to know someone who had moved abroad. One day my mum picked me up from primary school. She told me that we too were getting out of here. My reaction was "Yeah, sure!" But one month later I moved from present-day Lithuania to an industrial town called Nizhny Tagil in Russia, 1800km from Moscow. I would stay there with grandma. My mom is going to the Netherlands to build a future for us. My uncle, aunt and cousins were always around when I lived with my grandma. Not my dad though, he's not in the picture. My grandma is tough and old-fashioned. We didn't really have a

lot, she really loves me. I played a lot outdoors with anything I could find. We made our own fishing rods from bamboo to catch fish from the river, and we searched for mushrooms and berries in the forest. My family loves to cook, and my grandma taught me how to cook with everything I found. One of our favourites was potato pancakes. I baked them in the pan and served them with a lot of sour cream. I loved that my grandma trusted me to make them. The pancakes were our popcorn and dinner - we'd enjoy them while watching Mexican soap series - dubbed in Russian. I remember this part of my life as idyllic, even though we didn't always have water or electricity. Sometimes in the middle

of winter we would be without heating. Certain foods weren't always available in the supermarket, so the smallest things made me happy. Like Snickers or Mars bars which made it across the border about once a month. They cost 1000 rubles which is about 10 euros. My grandma or aunt would get me one twice a year, for my birthday and for Woman's Day. I ate the chocolate very slowly, really cherishing it. I lived with my grandma for one and a half years, but it felt like a really long time. I missed my mom a lot. But I had a really nice time with my family.

When I was 11 years old my mom came for me. We flew to Dusseldorf and took a train to Amsterdam. I had to give up my Russian and Lithuanian passport. Amsterdam was overwhelming, everything was different. I tried to take everything in. My mum took me to the playgrounds and parks. And when we went to the Albert Heijn supermarket I got a mixed bag of Snickers and Mars bars. I couldn't believe the abundance and how cheap it was! I ate so much that I got sick. So I never really ate it again. As I grew up, many people thought that I was Moroccan - I got my big black curly hair from my half-Armenian dad. I really liked that I could surprise them. So I started to play with it and asked them to guess where I'm from and usually gave them one hint: "It is the biggest country in the world by size." They would say China or Brazil. When I would tell them I'm Russian, often people would still not believe me. "Don't Russians have straight blond hair?" So I tried to explain that there are many Armenians in Russia since they were all part of the Soviet Union.

Today I am proud to be both Russian and Dutch. Even though I have lived here for so long, I don't want to forget where I came from. Because I'm very proud of my roots and what I have experienced. I never want to forget about this part. One day I tried to find

my father on this Russian social media platform, and ended up connecting with my half-brother instead. I figured if my father doesn't want to talk to me, then maybe I can talk to my brother. He was really kind, open and patient. My brother's warmth got me interested to learn more about where I came from. It was amazing and I got to ask him questions like "What did our father do all these years? What kind of father was he to you?" I jumped from question to question, it was all new to me. I still live in the old version of Russia. But Russia has changed a lot since I left.

I've realised that we often see our parents just as a parent, but they are so much more of course. My mom used to be a young girl. I remember she could play guitar and she was a good singer. She had me when she was 21, so there weren't many years before me. It makes me wonder how she lived her teenage years. And what about my grandma? How did she become the way she was? I want to ask her: "What made you so hard?" I'm thinking of interviewing them and then making a little booklet with a family tree with their stories. Add where they were born, where they moved to, who they fell in love with. I can even document my own life by asking them to share stories about me that I don't remember anymore. It's a bit scary to start these conversations, because I don't know what will come. But I can choose to challenge myself, or I can wonder for the rest of my life.

I'm dreaming of living the way I used to do with my grandma. I want to go back to basics and have a couple of sheep and chickens. I love to cook. With the influences from Amsterdam and my friends I prepare just about anything, from Japanese Yakitori to traditional Russian salads. I still prefer the Russian potato pancakes over popcorn.

04 SHARE

You've reflected, connected and explored your personal and collective histories. Now it's time to SHARE your insights. The SHARE process consists of two activities (1.5-4 hours in total):

Activities

1: What I have gained?

Learning Objectives

Digest and express key learnings from the REFLECT, CONNECT and EXPLORE sessions via meaningful and accessible forms of self-expression

2: What we can give each other?

Share key learnings from the REFLECT, CONNECT and EXPLORE sessions with each others

"Upon learning to do some of the 'male' or 'female' tasks, you will discover that many things you have been socialised into thinking were hard or boring, are actually really interesting or satisfying. But, of course, a small proportion of things will still remain deathly boring to some. This is also fine. At least it makes it easier to decide who does what."

– *Carmen*

1: What have I gained?

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Invite participants to make one of the following to digest and express their key learnings from the REFLECT, CONNECT and EXPLORE sessions via meaningful and accessible forms of self-expression: vlog, music playlist or collage. Have them accompany it with a letter addressed to (e.g., themselves in the future, their (future) grandchild, their parents, their grandparents, a prominent political or societal figure (past or present), etc.).

- Vlog: Browse through your phone for material or create new content to make a social media story or post to express your key reflections.
- Music playlist: Make a collection of songs that represents your key reflections. Use YouTube or Spotify to find the music, and use Google to look up lyrics and information about the artists and what the songs might mean.
- Collage: Gather together images and assemble them together to capture your key reflections.

Purpose

To enable participants to digest and express their key learnings from the REFLECT, CONNECT and EXPLORE sessions via meaningful and accessible forms of self-expression

Outcome

To individually reflect on key learnings

Time

45-120 minutes for creatively developing a vlog, music playlist or collage during a session or prior to it, depending on group logistics

Material

- Vlog: Smartphone or computer with internet access
- Music playlist: Headphones and a smartphone or computer with internet access
- Collage: Big piece of blank paper or cardboard (A4+) that will serve as the basis for the collage, (copies of) photos, colourful markers, old magazines and books, glue and scissors. Alternatively, create an online moodboard for free by using Canva, Miro or Google Jamboard
- Letter: Blank paper or computer with Word or similar

Preparation

- Set up beamer
- Download and use the slide deck above

Group Size

- 2+

2: What can we give each other?

Purpose

To enable participants to share their key learnings from the REFLECT, CONNECT and EXPLORE sessions with one another

Outcome

To collectively (within and beyond the learning group) reflect on key learnings

Time

45-120 minutes

Material

- In-person event: tape or other type of adhesive to hang collages, letters and the EXPLORE timeline; sound system; beamer; utensils and containers for serving food and drink, if applicable
- Online sharing: Headphones, smartphones or computers with internet access; dedicate website or Dropbox/Drive folder

Preparation

Remind participants to bring their finished products to the session (in case of in-person event) or upload them (in case of online sharing)

Group Size

- 2+

Source: Rehab Eldalil

Invite participants to share what they've made with their family members, friends and fellow community members. They may do this outside of the session itself. Alternatively, or in addition, educators/facilitators may wish to organise an in-person event or website to which participants can invite people meaningful to them to join or visit. In addition to presenting the timeline, consider setting up a gallery for the collages, screening the vlogs and play songs from the music playlists. If there is enough time and resources, add more fun to an in-person event experience by encouraging people to bring food and opportunities for collective sharing and storytelling into the mix! Check out the Roots Guide (pp. 256-57: 'Verhalen om de geest, ziel and maag te voeden') for some ideas.

Story

Meet

Carmen

Carmen was puzzled. The Hungarian man that approached her in the restaurant did not look anything like the bohemian man on the leaky boat from the Tinder profile picture. Peter was wearing a sleek suit and apologised that he had come straight from a conference at the European parliament. As he continued to talk about politics in a very formal manner, Carmen started to wonder whether the Tinder matching algorithm had made a mistake. Her Tinder blurb clearly stated ‘feminist’ and she was sure Peter’s profile matched hers. So Carmen decided to ask him about the boat. Peter instantly loosened up and in the conversation that followed his liberated personality and passion for the maritime lifestyle shone through. “Why don’t we travel the seas together?”, Carmen said jokingly at the end of the evening. One week later they set sail.

Carmen Ortiz Guillen was born in London, England in 1987 to parents from Colombia and Panama. Ever since she learned about the plight of her grandfather, who had to flee Panama after a fellow politician was assassinated, Carmen dreamt of becoming a journalist. Her devout grandparents ensured Carmen received a proper Catholic education in London since she was a little girl. While she longed to have deep conversations with her grandmother, unfortunately her Spanish was not fluent enough. Carmen therefore went to Colombia to study Spanish before moving to Honduras where she started work as a journalist. Her travels in central America came as a shock however. While she was exposed to chauvinism in London, nothing could prepare her for the inequality that

exists between men and women in Honduras. Her salvation came with the book A Brief History of Misogyny by Jack Holland, which gave Carmen insight into just how deeply rooted and pervasive sexism has been in human culture throughout the ages.

These insights proved to be quite the hurdle for Peter and Carmen, after the fresh lovebirds started their sailing adventure across Europe on Peter's small wooden boat. Quite naturally they took on classic male/female roles; Carmen, who grew up with arts and crafts, did the cooking and made curtains for the boat, while Peter, raised by an engineer father and grandfather, took charge of the plumbing and electricity. The charming little boat had seen better years though, and the ever-present dependence on Peter to fix the temperamental on-board generator, just so she could make some pancakes, started to take its toll on Carmen. "I actually struggled a bit relying on Peter to fix my problems, so I asked him to show me how to fix the generator and electricity." Peter replied it would take too long. "Luckily, Peter is a very open and sympathetic guy," however, and, after Carmen insisted it would be worth the investment, they decided to mix up the traditional roles on the boat. Peter taught Carmen how to use a saw, sander and power tools. And even though Carmen didn't particularly want to learn how to fix the toilet, she was informed it was a mandatory part of the package. Working at sea together strengthened their relationship.

On a particularly dark and stormy night in Amsterdam Noorderpark, Carmen was on board with two Airbnb guests from Italy, while Peter was back home in Budapest. The poor aged boat struggled to withstand the onslaught from the waves and rain, and as the electricity conked out Carmen heard leaks springing all over. "No worries, I can fix it myself," Carmen thought to herself as she

applied her carpenter and electrician skills to fix the electricity. Not long after she fell asleep with a satisfactory smile on her face, Carmen woke up as she noticed the boat was moving weirdly. When she got out on deck, she realised the storm had pulled the wooden anchoring post out of the soil and the boat was adrift. Terrified that the boat's fragile wooden body would crash into the opposite bank and sink, Carmen jumped into the sea in her pyjamas, desperately trying to drag the ship back again to its designated spot in the park. When the Italian guests came out on the deck in a sleepy haze to see what all the commotion was about, Carmen was frantically hammering the wooden stake back into the wet soil. But the stake was too short and the soil was too wet. Thankfully, Carmen's neighbour offered his large anchoring pole that would secure the boat. After the ordeal of midnight shenanigans had come to an end, the Airbnb guests packed their bags and left in a hurry, leaving a soaked, but very proud Carmen behind.

When Carmen realised human culture has ingrained traditional gender roles into the population, it encouraged her not to accept them. She is ever so grateful that she pushed to break these roles at sea with Peter, as it is the equal share of labour that creates a harmonious and respectful environment. "You'll always have different areas of interest, and that's ok, but it's important to know how to do each other's tasks if push comes to shove. Upon learning to do some of the 'male' or 'female' tasks, you will discover that many things you have been socialised into thinking were hard or boring, are actually really interesting or satisfying. But of course a small proportion of things will still remain deathly boring to some. This is also fine. At least it makes it easier to decide who does what."

The way forward

Wow - you've reached the end of your Roots Guide journey! If you're anything like us, you might need some time to process all your new impressions of diversity, migration, heritage, identity, belonging and inclusion. No matter how this journey has been for you, we hope you have gained new insights into how we are all interconnected - inside and outside your teaching spaces. But most of all, we hope you discovered something new about yourself along the way and the power of providing spaces to explore ourselves, others and our places and roles in the world around us.

We hope that this tool makes the new requirement to teach citizenship education empowering, meaningful and fun for your students and yourself. Perhaps now you have more answers to the question "What kinds of citizens are we and do we want to be?" Perhaps now you have even more questions than you did when you began – and, if so, that's brilliant!

Keep on being curious – and brave enough – to explore yourself and the situations we currently find ourselves in, and to imagine and prepare ourselves collectively for a future for all of us. Your curiosity made you use this toolkit. Curiosity drives learning. And it's why we created Roots Guide. On behalf of the Roots Guide team and guides, thank you for including us as one of your resources and guides on this great journey.

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